

POLICY BRIEF COMMON TEMPLATE

RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES

INTRODUCTION: PROJECT TITLE AND PROJECT OBJECTIVES

CALL: HORIZON-INFRA-2021-DEV-02

(Developing and consolidating the European research infrastructures landscape, maintaining global leadership (2021))

TOPIC: [Promoting balanced multilingualism in open science and scholarly communication](#)

PROJECT: On the road to sustainability: paving the way for OPERAS as an efficient open Social Sciences and Humanities scholarly communication Research Infrastructure (OPERAS-PLUS)

<https://operas-eu.org>

PROJECT: objectives

The general objective of the OPERAS-PLUS project is to provide the necessary support OPERAS needs to complete its preparatory phase and to transition its status into an ERIC.

This general objective is divided in several specific objectives (SOs), defined by the topic description, the recommendations provided by the ESFRI report and the issues raised by the OPERAS General Assembly in 2021:

(SO1) To develop and strengthen OPERAS governance structure, esp. financial, legal, and human resource management aspects of the infrastructure central hub in a sustainable way, compliant with RI management best practices.

(SO2) To support the establishment and development of OPERAS national nodes, set up and manage their relations with the central hub.

(SO3) To develop OPERAS portfolio of services by providing both required technology and a monitoring system for services development.

(SO4) To maximise OPERAS' impact in the ERA and at international level by extending it beyond its current scope and onboarding new members and countries in the infrastructure.

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POLICY IMPLICATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Multilingualism represents a core stake in today's world, as it is considered as one of the pillars of an inclusive, pluralistic, equitable, and sustainable society. With specific regard to Open Science and scholarly communication, multilingualism plays a crucial role in creating research impact, preserving locally-relevant scientific work, and fostering interaction between science and society, as pointed out by the [Helsinki Initiative](#) in 2019. To support this vision, which establishes multilingualism as a cornerstone of Open Science, trust in research, and equitable knowledge dissemination, OPERAS has been promoting the concept of "balanced multilingualism"¹, which intends to challenge the hegemony of English in sciences while encouraging reasonable and sustainable approaches for the production and dissemination of multilingual research content. While recognising the crucial role of a shared language facilitating international exchanges within the global scientific community, OPERAS believes that using a *lingua franca* should not mean implicitly imposing a *lingua unica* in scholarly communication. Research shows² in fact that the benefits of publishing in English in the current landscape – increased prestige, outreach and

¹ Sivertsen (2018), Balula and Leão (2019)

² See for example Amano, T. et al. (2023), Kelsey, H. et al. (2024), Guédon, J-C. et al. (2019).

collaboration opportunities – do not come without consequences. Firstly, this linguistic dominance hinders information sharing and co-construction of knowledge, not only among researchers, but also in science communication, citizen science and participatory research activities, which are all the more important in an age of disinformation and mistrust. Moreover, imposing a language – including and especially to non-native speakers – limits intellectual creativity and thought, thus paving the way to standardisation of knowledge production and dissemination, to the detriment of local research and bibliodiversity. To tackle these challenges, the idea of “balanced multilingualism” introduces “a dynamic approach”, which considers and values a variety of “communication purposes in all different areas of research, and all the languages needed to fulfil these purposes, in a holistic manner without exclusions or priorities.” As per the same definition, balanced multilingualism also consists in establishing “instruments for documenting and measuring the use of language for all the different purposes in research, thereby providing the basis for the monitoring of further globalization of research in a more responsible direction.”

In order to translate this vision into practical objectives and actions, OPERAS has undertaken and promotes the following efforts:

- **Advocate for robust national publishing infrastructures and collaborate with national nodes** to strengthen open science practices and policy development aimed at fostering scholarly publishing in multiple languages. OPERAS national nodes play a critical role in this effort by supporting diverse linguistic communities.
- **Develop multilingual discovery platforms and databases.** Initiatives like GoTriple – whose platform is operated by OPERAS – provide access to multilingual or language-agnostic discovery tools, fostering global collaboration and inclusivity.
- **Explore how to leverage technology-aided translation tools.** OPERAS actively develops prototype tools (i.e. the collaborative translation platform Mondaecus) and produces reports (i.e. the Translations and Open Science exploratory studies³) to suggest workflows and best practices for technology-aided multilingual content production, ensuring discoverability and accessibility for different audiences.
- **Encourage innovation.** OPERAS supports the development of diverse dissemination formats to enhance multilingual communication: blog posts, long and plain-language summaries, etc.
- **Promote non-for-profit publishing models.** Through initiatives like DIAMAS and ALMASI, OPERAS supports equitable and sustainable open-access publishing, ensuring accessibility and inclusivity in scholarly communication, including from a linguistic perspective⁴.
- **Advocate for reform in research assessment.** OPERAS partners with initiatives such as CoARA and GraspOS to push for assessment frameworks that value diverse forms of scholarly communication in all languages, without exclusions or priorities.
- **Establish connections and improve discoverability across languages and disciplines.** The LUMEN project – in which OPERAS is actively involved – relies on existing multilingual disciplinary platforms to advance cross-domain and cross-language collaboration and discovery processes in four academic fields: Mathematics (Maths), Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH), Earth Systems (ES) and Molecular Dynamics (MD).

Based on the experience acquired and the feedback received from the community, OPERAS therefore promotes the following **recommendations**:

1. Support multilingual publishing and assessment policies that give full scientific legitimacy to all languages.
2. Foster bibliodiverse and linguistically inclusive publishing ecosystems by strengthening and valuing regional, non-profit and local-language publishers.
3. Develop sustainable open science infrastructures and expert networks that foster multilingual research preservation and international collaboration.
4. Advocate for high-quality translation to be fully recognised as a scholarly output.

³ Fiorini, S. (2024). Exploratory studies for the creation of a technology-aided collaborative translation service in open scholarly communication. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10972986>

⁴ Creating multilingual resources through community-driven collaboration. DIAMAS project.

<https://diamasproject.eu/creating-multilingual-resources-through-community-driven-collaboration/>

5. Promote and value not only interlingual but also intralingual translation in order to produce innovative communication formats and make scientific languages and publications understandable across different domains and audiences.
 6. Invest in the development of language-agnostic discovery tools with integrated open translation platforms.
 7. Identify efficient use cases for language technology tools to help produce and disseminate multilingual content according to specific communication purposes: translation and writing aid for authors and translators, (semi-)automatic translation for metadata, information or assessment purposes, technology-aided collaborative translation, etc.
 8. Establish and promote guidelines to ensure that the ethical and legal implications of using artificial intelligence are taken into account in multilingual content production, evaluation and search.
 9. Encourage the adoption of open-source and/or community-led language technology tools to foster tailored, fair, transparent, human-centric and independent strategies for technology development and usage.
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